

Processing Crawled Data

M.A.C.J. Overmeer MSc (Mark)*, MarkOv Solutions, Arnhem, The Netherlands

Abstract

Building an internet-wide search engine starts by collecting and pre-processing the content of webpages. There are dozens of initiatives to crawl for page content to build a text search interface. However, there is a huge difference between performing a text search as such, and presenting quality search results. To be able to put a label “best match” on a fragment of text, a considerable number of additional complex algorithms must be implemented. Those require far more resources than the full text search database.

The “Crawl Pipeline” project combines many kinds of information collection activities: provides those additional algorithms with the facts they need for their work. The Pipeline is also used to collect facts which are not search engine related, like counting web-server types, detecting expired certificates, or discovering phishing sites.

PIPELINE

Project “Crawl Pipeline” provides a base infrastructure to extract information from web content. The software may be run as post-processing step on a web-crawler, but in its initial set-up, it runs on dedicated hardware. It is able to process Terabytes per day per pipeline instance, potentially with a few dozen pipelines in parallel.

A crawler instance has a list of URLs (pages to visit) as input. For each URL, the crawl sends a request to a website. The response contains some data we need. Meanwhile, metadata is collected too. The triplet (request, response, metadata) is often written into WARC archives[1], or into a database. At that moment, it becomes a static data-set. The Pipeline transforms those static data-sets back into a stream of collection actions for interested parties to filter and extract into the data they need.

The Pipeline spends time to reconstruct the crawl, just as each user would need when processing the data-set on their own. Probably even a bit more time. But once the crawl is restored, it is reused for many purposes. Those activities are abstracted into Tasks: per end-user a separate Task.

(EXTERNAL) TASKS

Researchers who need data for their investigations can submit “external Tasks” for the Pipeline. OSF search engine support components will also implement Tasks to enhance its knowledge.

Each Task description contains:

- filter rules to select answers;
- simple data extraction steps; and
- packaging instructions.

The Task will reduce the amount of data for their requesters down to only a few percent of the original data size. Usually from Terabyte down to Gigabyte scale per day.

Many research projects can get their minor subset of crawl-data without the expense of processing Terabytes of data themselves. Besides, they do not need to implement communication with each crawler instance which will emerge in the near future.

RUNNING THE PIPELINE

The main components of the pipeline instance are

- incoming feed collects the static crawl data-sets published by crawlers;
- batch control manages a set of processing queues;
- each queue reconstructs one crawl result set at a time;
- each result is passed to each of the defined Tasks sequentially;
- when a result is selected for a Task, the related extract is made;
- after a short time, at most a day, the extracts are packaged in the way which is also defined in the Task; and finally
- the packaged results must be retrieved within a day, otherwise they get lost.

PRESENTING

The presentation will show which kind of Tasks can be run on the “Crawl Pipeline”: how can you use the facility to support your own research. It will also show challenges and opportunities for (near) future extensions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] The WARC File Format – ISO 28500

* mark@overmeer.net